

PRO-COAST preregistration: religiosity, political ideology, and civic pro-environmental behaviour

What's the main question being asked in this study?

How is religiosity associated with civic pro-environmental behaviour, and to what extent is this relationship moderated by political ideology?

Parameters of interest

Because the hypothesis of exactly zero effect is never true (Orben & Lakens, 2020), rather than seeking evidence against null hypotheses, we use Bayesian analysis to examine the probability that given parameters have values in given regions. “Explore”, “predict”, and “meaningful” are formally defined in terms of such regions in the “Regions of interest” section.

Definition: CPEB is civic pro-environmental behaviour.

Parameter 1: We explore the association between religiosity and CPEB *not* controlling for right-wing ideology, without prediction.

Parameter 2: We predict meaningful variation in the between-case-study association between religiosity and CPEB *not* controlling for right-wing ideology.

Parameter 3: We explore the association between religiosity and CPEB *but* controlling for right-wing ideology, without prediction.

Parameter 4: We predict meaningful variation in the between-case-study association between religiosity and CPEB *but* controlling for right-wing ideology.

Parameter 5: We predict a negative association between right-wing ideology and CPEB, controlling for religiosity.

Parameter 6: We predict meaningful variation in the between-case-study association between right-wing ideology and CPEB, controlling for religiosity.

Parameter 7: We predict that the association between religiosity and CPEB is moderated by right-wing ideology, such that the association becomes more negative with increasing right-wing ideology.

Parameter 8: We predict meaningful variation between case studies in the extent to which the association between religiosity and CPEB is moderated by right-wing ideology.

Parameters 3 to 8 each have two versions, one where right-wing ideology is operationalised as social conservatism, and one where it is operationalised as a left-right scale. We register a primary interest in social conservatism and treat the left-right scale as an additional check. This is for two reasons: (1) the left-right scale will be entirely missing in one case study; and (2) we have a theoretical hunch that social conservatism better represents the specific aspects of right-wing ideology that are most relevant for our predictions.

Key variables

DV: civic pro-environmental behaviour (CPEB) – composite of three items:

“I participate in protests against current environmental conditions.” (A26)

“I participate in events organised by environmental groups.” (A27)

“I vote for a government proposing environmentally conscious policies.” (A28)

Response options: Disagree (1) to Agree (5), Prefer not to say, Missing (no response)

IV1: religiosity – single item:

“How religious would you consider yourself?” (F7)

Response options: Not at all religious (1) to Very religious (5), Prefer not to say, Missing (no response)

IV2: political ideology, option 1, social conservatism – composite of two items:

“Discrimination and disadvantage against women must be eliminated.” (Reverse coded) (F9)

“The different ways of life and increasing diversity in [OWN COUNTRY] enrich us.” (Reverse coded) (F16)

Response options: Disagree (1) to Agree (5), Prefer not to say, Missing (no response)

IV2: political ideology, option 2, left-right ideology scale – single item:

“In political matters, people talk of “the left” and “the right”. How would you place your views on this scale, generally speaking?” (F17)

Response options: Left (1) to Right (7), Don't know, Prefer not to say, Missing (no response)

Random factor: case study identity, with nine levels.

Control covariates

Gender – single nominal item:

“Gender” (F1)

Response options: Man, Woman, Non-binary, Other, Prefer not to say, Missing (no response)

Education – single item:

“What is the highest educational level that you have attained?” (F4)

Response options: No formal education (1) to PhD or equivalent (7), Prefer not to say, Missing (no response)

Variable pre-processing

Religiosity, education, left-right ideology, and economic situation are single Likert items but are treated as continuous predictors. Gender has been measured as multiple categories, but these will be collapsed to a binary variable non-man (woman, non-binary, other) vs man. All “Prefer not to say” responses will be set to missing. “Don’t know” (left-right ideology only) will be set to the neutral scale point (4).

Composite variables (CPEB and social conservatism) will be formed as the mean of z-transformed individual items, thus they will be validly defined unless all items are missing. If CPEB has a Cronbach’s $\alpha < 0.5$, the item which most increases alpha by dropping will be dropped, or A28 if no item increases α . Two-item composites (social conservatism or an item-dropped CPEB) will not be used if $r < 0.3$. In that case, for social conservatism, the single item F16 will be used, and for CPEB, the single item A27 will be used.

All variables (including binary gender) will be standardised (z-transformed) prior to use in registered models.

Model specification

Bayesian models will be constructed with the R package brms function `brm()`, with default arguments unless otherwise specified. The model formula for determining Parameters 1 and 2 is:

Model 1: `cpeb ~ gender + education + religiosity + (1 + religiosity | | case_study)`

The model formula for determining Parameters 3 to 7 is:

Model 2: $cpeb \sim \text{gender} + \text{education} + \text{religiosity} + \text{ideology} + \text{religiosity} : \text{ideology} + (1 + \text{religiosity} + \text{ideology} || \text{case_study})$

The model formula for determining Parameter 8 is:

Model 3: $cpeb \sim \text{gender} + \text{education} + \text{religiosity} + \text{ideology} + \text{religiosity} : \text{ideology} + (1 + \text{religiosity} + \text{ideology} + \text{religiosity} : \text{ideology} || \text{case_study})$

Model 3 adds to Model 2 the random slope for the interaction term, which is Parameter 8. This term is omitted from Model 2 because given anticipated sample (see below), the model may struggle to define a three-way interaction involving a random variable, which could interfere with estimation of Parameters 3 to 7.

To confirm appropriate model fit, two diagnostic plots will be examined: residuals vs fitted values (scatterplot), and residuals vs group (boxplot) will be examined. Models will be adjusted as necessary (for example by modelling residual standard deviation as a function of case study if relevant heteroscedasticity is observed).

If missingness in either of the control covariates (gender and education) reduces the number of complete cases by more than 5% of what would be non-missing without that covariate, that control covariate will be dropped. If both control covariates have this effect, the one that causes most data to be lost will be dropped first. After dropping one control variable, the other will be dropped if it reduces the new number of complete cases by more than 5%. If CPEB has been reduced to a single item, “family = cumulative()” will be used to construct the model. Missingness in non-control variables causes data-dropping (there will be no imputation).

Priors

To obtain the full advantages of Bayesian analysis, for our primary analysis we set priors that are as informative as possible (Table 1).

Table 1. Prior distributions and justification.

Parameter	Prior	Prior justification
Gender (non-man) β	Gaussian (M = 0.0321, SD = 0.2581)	Mean calculated from 28-country data-summary of petition-signing by gender (Isaacson, 2024). SD derived from Pearson’s r distribution across 322 meta-analyses of effect sizes across social psychology (Richard et al., 2003).
Education β	Gaussian (M = 0.13, SD = 0.2581)	Mean obtained from 33-country meta-analysis of Pearson’s r for environmental policy support (Bergquist et al., 2022). SD as per gender.
Religiosity β	Gaussian (M = 0, SD = 0.2581)	The best available study of cross-European data notes a negative association, but does not provide compatible parameterisation (Saroglou et al., 2025); other large international studies find positive associations (e.g., Zemo & Nigus, 2021); there is therefore insufficient confidence for a directional prior. SD as per gender.
Ideology β	Gaussian (M = 0, SD = 0.2581)	Although theory leads to a directional prediction, we could not find a meta-analysis or cross-national study with an outcome variable closely related enough to relevant behaviour, hence a mean of zero. SD as per gender.

Ideology : Religiosity β	Gaussian (M = 0, SD = 0.2581)	As per ideology main effect.
Religiosity σ	Student's t (M = 0.1221, scale = 0.0852, df = 4.1561)	Best fitting Student's t for a dataset containing inter-study variation estimates from 360 meta-analyses of studies reporting Pearson's r from across the field of psychology (van Erp et al., 2017).
Ideology σ		
Ideology : Religiosity σ		

Note. β distributions are for standardised fixed regression coefficients. σ distributions are for the case-study random slopes (note these are always zero-truncated as variation cannot be negative). All derivations and calculations are described in full at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20181224>.

As informative or directional priors can cause concern for those more familiar with frequentist paradigms, we note that (1) we have no directional priors for our key predictors, religiosity, and ideology, and (2) we will also report robustness tests where we repeat the analyses with `brm()` default priors, which are entirely flat for fixed β , and very wide (and thus uninformative) for random σ (Student's t with mean 0, scale 2.5, and df 3).

Regions of interest

Terms used when defining our parameters of interest are themselves defined in the following way.

Predict: This focuses on the posterior for the relevant β and signifies an intention to report (1) the probability that the parameter value is in the predicted direction and (2) the median and 95% credible interval for that posterior.

Explore: The same as predict, except that the probability of direction concerns the observed rather than predicted direction.

Meaningful variation: This focuses on the posterior for the relevant random slope σ . Since variation parameters cannot be less than zero, estimating the probability of meaningful variation requires defining a lower threshold. We use the 20th percentile (0.0708) of the prior distribution for inter-study variation derived from the above-introduced van Erp et al. (2017) study. The reported probability of meaningful variation is therefore the probability that inter-case-study variation exceeds the variation seen in the lowest 20% of available inter-study comparisons. We also report the median and 95% credible interval for the posterior.

Sample determination

Data collection is underway, but researchers have not accessed data at the point of preregistration. The data will be all data collected by the PRO-COAST consortium stakeholder survey Wave 2 up until 13:00 CET 2026-06-01. The anticipated sample size is somewhere between 600 and 900. If the sample is less than 600 at that point, or if any single case-study has produced less than 50 data points, data collection will be extended for exactly 7 days. There are no reasons for excluding data other than any listed above.

References

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